
**The Socio-Economic Essence of the Concept "Ecotourism" in the Development of Ecological
Tourism**

Ibodullaev Nurali Eshniyazovich

SamIES, associate professor of the "Tourism" department

***Abstract.** Today, in Uzbekistan, great importance is attached to the rapid development of the tourism sector, and as one of the objectives and priorities of the state policy in the field of tourism in the medium-term perspective, "...to give tourism the status of a strategic sector of the economy, to be the leading force in the comprehensive and rapid development of this sector in all regions and interrelated industries turning the economy into a powerful tool for diversification, structural change and sustainable development...*

***Keywords:** tourism, service, tourists, reception, ecotourism.*

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of these tasks requires the development of ecological tourism in the regions, providing the population with new jobs, in-depth analysis of the tourist and recreational market, and the development of relevant programs.

It is known that the approaches to tourism and ecotourism in Western, European, Eastern and CIS countries differ from each other. Therefore, the tariffs of the specific concept of "ecotourism" were considered, having studied the existing types and forms of ecotourism.

The emergence of the concept of "ecotourism" was caused by several trends:

First, tourism has emerged as a major global economic activity. The number of visitors to protected areas around the world has increased to such an extent that the damage they can cause to the natural complex is a serious concern. On the other hand, it became inevitable that the rational organization of tourism would financially support nature conservation and increase the importance of natural areas that should be preserved in the first place. Therefore, tourism will have to "work" for nature protection, that is, the protected areas will have to "earn money for themselves";

secondly, protected activities will be difficult to succeed by merely restricting or prohibiting them, especially if they are against the interests of the local population. The local population should become a direct partner of this activity and a careful attitude to nature should be beneficial for them, and tourism should play a leading role in this;

thirdly, there have been changes in the aspirations of tourists. More and more people, especially in industrialized countries, are seeking to get out of the big cities and into the heart of the unspoiled

countryside. As opposed to the traditional "beach-resort" type of recreation, the demand for active-conscious types has increased.

The concept of ecological tourism as one of the important means of sustainable development of natural areas was created in the context of the important nature protection, economic and social problems of our time.

Some concepts and terms presented in scientific literature in most cases only partially illuminate the essence of the concept of "ecological tourism". As an example of the versatility of existing definitions, we can cite the following:

"Ecotourism is a type of nature-oriented tourism that includes environmental education and enlightenment and is a form of tourism that is implemented on the basis of the principles of ecological sustainability."

"Ecological tourism is purposeful travel to natural areas for the purpose of further study of the local culture and natural environment, without violating the integrity of the existing ecosystems and providing for the protection of the natural resources available to the local population."

"Ecotourism is an ecologically sustainable form of natural tourism, which is mainly focused on living and understanding wildlife with minimal impact on the environment, reducing consumption and costs while respecting ethical standards. Usually, this form of tourism is carried out in protected areas.

"While ecotourism allows for the protection and development of nature, it implies at least the establishment of positive synergistic relations between tourism activities, biodiversity and the local population, and the appropriate organization and management of these activities."

"Ecotourism is tourism that is carried out in intact natural areas, does not harm the environment and its quality, and directly contributes to the protection of natural areas and their effective management."

"Ecotourism is a planned type of tourism that combines the enjoyment of nature and living things, has a positive impact on environmental protection, positively affects the living standards of local social groups, and envisages sustainable development that is just for both people and nature. is tourism".

"Ecotourism includes 3 main criteria: attractions that attract tourists are natural (for example, flora, fauna, geological features) and the features of the cultural environment are important, and the main focus is on the soft impact on the natural resources of the region. Ecotourism is interconnected with the concept of sustainable tourism, beneficial to local communities, residents, and should not exceed the recreational capacity of the regions.

The International Union for Conservation of Nature defines ecotourism as "travel to relatively undisturbed natural areas to explore and enjoy cultural sites, without harming the environment, and ensuring the socio-economic active participation of local people and their benefit from these activities."

A similar definition is given by "Ecotourism Society" (The Ecotourism Society): "Ecotourism is a trip that contributes to the protection of nature and improves the well-being of the local population while feeling responsible for natural areas."

In the scientific works of German, Austrian and Swiss experts, the term "ecological and socially responsible tourism" is used instead of "soft tourism". In our opinion, although this term is long and complicated, it more accurately reflects the content and essence of "soft" tourism. In recent years, the

term 'sustainability' has become more widely used in the English-language literature, and there is an attempt to link ecotourism with the use of intact (or less disturbed) and protected natural landscapes.

Among the Russian scientists E. Yu. Ledovsky, A. V. Drozdov, N. V. Moraleva, "ecotourism corresponds to ecological and social requirements, feels responsibility towards nature, contributes to its protection, performs an educational task, treats traditional cultural and local communities with care it increases the culture of the tourists.

BTT defines ecotourism as "ecological tourism - a trip to the uninhabited corners of nature", and the World Wildlife Fund defines it as "ecotourism - natural tourism that helps to protect nature".

Definitions of ecotourism often include achieving sustainability, reducing negative impacts on nature, increasing economic returns for environmental development, or enhancing environmental education. Therefore, a very simple and conceptual definition is given by Craig Lindberg: "Ecotourism is a sustainable and nature-oriented tourism and recreation activity, which implies a mutual balance of ecological, socio-cultural and economic impacts of tourism."

In the development of ecotourism, along with its essence, goals and tasks, special attention should be paid to the principles of its organization, planning and management. Because any industry has different aspects, features, basic principles of its organization, planning and management, different types of tourism.

Tseballos-Lascurein's research argues that adventure tourism is not ecotourism, citing that although travelers' perceptions of the places and areas they visit are broadened, they do not have a positive impact on natural areas.

In Khumbu, Nepal, although the local population has gained income through tourism activities, the employment system and culture of the population have been disrupted and stratification has increased. Thus, although the visitors call themselves eco-tourists, in reality they are derailing the natural and cultural environment. Therefore, in many countries, tourists are not taken to the tour areas in helicopters, so as not to scare the animals, or in motorized gasoline boats, so as not to pollute the water bodies. In general, both positive and negative experiences of ecotourism development can be found not only in foreign countries, but also in our republic.

Therefore, for the preservation of nature, not the real scale of tourism or the promotion of tourists, but the impact of their travel on nature is the main place. It depends on how the trip is organized. More precisely, 10 unplanned and unmonitored tourists can cause more damage to nature than 100 people. At the same time, in many developed countries of the world, thousands of tourists come to national parks to stay for a few days, pay for specially equipped visitor centers and eco-trails, and provide income for NGOs and local residents without harming the environment. Therefore, they can be called eco-tourists in a sense, considering that they spend many days traveling through the complex wildlife, with backpacks on their shoulders and tents for the night.

So, according to the above, ecotourism today is a complex, interdisciplinary field that ensures the interaction of tourism, nature and culture protection.

Ecotourism is directly related to other types of tourism, when Hector Tseballos-Lascurein introduced the term "ecotourism" to science in 1983, there were 30 similar and related concepts.

Natural tourism (nature tourism, nature-based or nature-oriented tourism) - voluntary types of tourism related to the use of natural resources such as landscape, relief, water, plants and wild animals in an unchanged state. The main difference between ecotourism and natural tourism is that it is aimed at promoting tourists (wilderness recreation, trekking, swimming, hunting, etc.) and does not take into account ecological, social and other sustainability.

As a form of natural tourism, there are biotourism (wildlife tourism) and travel to wild nature (wilderness travel), the main purpose of which are objects of living nature, individual species and biocenoses.

Sustainable tourism is considered as a relatively broader concept. According to the definition of BTT and Tourism and Travel Council, sustainable tourism meets the needs of tourists visiting tourist centers and the residents of the centers. Sustainable tourism must meet the criteria of social, cultural, ecological and economic acceptability. Sustainable tourism should be adapted to specific ethnic and cultural characteristics in the long term, meet the requirements of social justice, be ecologically acceptable and economically profitable.

According to Tseballos Lascurein, tourism is the preservation of natural resources for an unlimited period of time. Sustainable tourism in a broader sense is the use of all types of natural and artificial resources that contribute to the sustainable development of tourism.

Sustainable tourism is a general concept suitable for all types of tourism. The concepts of "sustainable" and "development" (BTT) are emphasized. For example, the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency follows 10 principles of sustainable tourism:

1. Economical and sustainable use of natural resources;
2. Reducing excess consumption and waste;
3. Ensuring preservation of natural, social and cultural diversity;
4. Deep planning, complex approach, integration of ecotourism into regional development plans;
5. Support of the local economy;
6. Participation of local population in the development of tourism and distribution of financial and other funds from this activity among them;
7. Giving advice to interested parties;
8. Training of employees;
9. Responsible tourism marketing;
10. Ecotourism is oriented towards nature and is located at the "crossroads" of sustainable tourism.

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